

"INFORMATION COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN"

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Annotation. The Concept of Modernization of the Republic of Uzbekistan and our general education sets an important task: to prepare the younger generation for life in a rapidly changing information society, in a world in which the process of emergence of new knowledge is accelerating, there is a constant need for new professions, for continuous professional development. And the key role in solving these problems is played by modern man's possession of Information Computer Technologies. The 21st century is the era of the information society.

Key words: russian language, secondary school, Russian literature, higher school, Internet, information technology.

Currently, there is an increasing increase in the influence of media technologies on a person. This has a particularly strong effect on a child who would rather watch TV than read a book. A powerful flow of new information, advertising, the use of computer technology on television, the distribution of game consoles, electronic toys and computers have a great impact on the upbringing of a child and his perception of the world around him. The nature of his favorite practical activity - games - is also changing significantly, and his favorite characters and hobbies are changing. Previously, a child could receive information on any topic through various channels: a textbook, reference literature, a teacher's lecture, a lesson summary. But, today, taking into account modern realities, the teacher must introduce new methods of presenting information into the educational process. The question arises why this is necessary. The child's brain, tuned to receive knowledge in the form of entertainment programs on television, will much more easily perceive the information offered in the lesson with the help of media. [3, 271]

It is necessary to teach each child in a short period of time to master, transform and use huge amounts of information in practical activities. It is very important to organize the learning process so that the child actively, with interest and passion worked in the classroom, saw the fruits of his labor and could evaluate them.

A combination of traditional teaching methods and modern information technologies, including computer ones, can help the teacher in solving this difficult task. After all, using a computer in the classroom allows you to make the learning process mobile, strictly differentiated and individual.

Combining the capabilities of a TV, a video recorder, a book, a calculator, being a universal toy capable of imitating other toys and a variety of games, a modern computer at the same time is an equal partner for a child, capable of responding very subtly to his actions and requests, which he sometimes lacks. On the other hand, this method of teaching is also very attractive for teachers: it helps them better assess the abilities and knowledge of the child, understand him, encourages them to look for new, non-traditional forms and methods of teaching [2, 90].

In practice, information technologies of training are called all technologies using special technical information tools (computers, audio, video, fragments from movies). [1, 147]

When computers became widely used in education, the term "new information technology" appeared. Any pedagogical technology is an information technology, since the basis of the technological learning process is information and its transformation. A better term for computer-based learning technologies is computer technology.

Computer (new information) learning technologies are the process of preparing and transmitting information to the learner, the means of which is a computer, laptop, tablet. [3, 97]

The computer gives the teacher new opportunities, allowing together with the student to enjoy the fascinating process of cognition, not only by the power of

imagination pushing the walls of the school office, but with the help of the latest technologies allows you to immerse yourself in a bright colorful world. Such an activity causes emotional uplift in children, even lagging students are willing to work with a computer. Increasing motivation and cognitive activity due to the variety of forms of work, the possibility of including a game moment: if you solve the examples correctly, you open the picture, insert all the letters correctly, you will move the fairy-tale hero closer to the goal [4, 67].

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